

STRESS ANALYSIS OF A GRP/PVC SANDWICH T-JOINT

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ABSTRACT

Stress distribution in a GRP/PVC sandwich T-joint is analyzed by a linear two-dimensional finite element method. Such joints are commonly used in high speed marine vehicles. Particular attention is paid to the complex stress picture in the area of the attachment lap, the glue and the laminates of the two sandwich panels. The stress analysis is applied to predict possible locations of failure initiation.

KEYWORDS: Sandwich; Laminate; Core; Glue; Finite Element Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels [1] composed of laminates with two thin strong sheets of dense material which are glued to a thick core made of a light and relatively soft low strength material, are attractive components of high speed marine vehicles. The laminates are made by glass or carbon fibres embedded in polyester, epoxy or vinylester matrix. The core is generally made of plastic foam, honeycomb or some other material [2-5].

The vessels are made of deck, side, bottom and bulkhead panels which are connected in T- and L-shape joints. Such joints need to transfer tension and compression in the cross-panel (A, in

Fig. 1) into bending and shear in the main panel as well as shear in the panel planes. Information about such joints is rather incomplete. The aim of this work is to shed some light into the performance of the behaviour of sandwich T-joints. Closed form analytical solutions of the displacements and stresses are impossible to achieve. Hence, a finite element method is applied, considering linear elastic behaviour. Computed distributions of direct and shear stresses across and through the core material, the glue and the attachment-lap are given when the panel A of the T-joint is exposed to a pull-out force.

2. NATURE OF THE PROBLEM

The T-joint considered is depicted in Fig. 1, and is composed of a PVC-core and GRP laminates, based on E-glass and polyester. The two panels are kept together with glue in the contact face together with a GRP attachment lap outside the laminates, as shown in Fig. 1. The T-joint is exposed to a tension force normal to the flange (Fig. 2). Some insight in the physical behaviour of the joint has been obtained by laboratory testing [6]. The experimental set up is shown in Fig. 2. The load is applied through an hydraulic piston and is transferred through two steel pieces which are glued to the laminates (Fig. 2). So, the axial forces in the sandwich T-joint will be carried by the laminates of the panel A and transmitted locally into the transverse sandwich (panel B).

In the experimental tests force-displacement characteristics are obtained for different attachment configurations [6]. Two major failure modes are observed:

- (I) Failure in the laminates, the core of the panel A, the glue and the attachment lap.
- (II) Shear fracture of the core in the panel B.

From the experiments a significant scatter in the measured results was observed and there is no significant differences in the ultimate load of the two failure modes [6]. In the dominant failure mechanism (I), the fracture may start at defects in the microstructure, such as air pores in the glue or initial debondings between the glue and the core material or between the glue and the laminates. Fig. 3 depicts possible initial crack or debond configurations at the connection between laminates, the

glue, the core of the panel A and the attachment lap. But what is the likely initial crack size(s) and their spatial distribution? These questions are not easily answered. A further observation is that there is a singularity at the interface corner A (Fig. 3) where the glue, laminate and the core material meet and at the interface corners B, C and D, where the laminate, glue and the lap meet. The local geometry of the interface corners is shown in Figure 3. Such singularities exist if the corner is sharp, as it happens in this problem. The strength of these singularities depend on the local geometry, the Young's modulus as well as the Poisson's ratio of the laminate the core and the glue material. So, a crack initiation may take place in four different positions.

In this study, assuming linear elastic behaviour and no defects or debondings in the glue are, we clarify the stress picture in order to find out where the highest stresses appear and which parameters the strength depend on.

3. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

A joint with dimensions and material properties which are typical for bulkhead-to-hull GRP/PVC sandwich T-joint is considered. The face sheets of the sandwich panels consist of two layers of 800 g/m² each, woven E-glass with fibers in +45- and -45-directions [$\pm 45 \pm 45$]. One layer of standard AI-reinforcement consists of 400 g/m² woven E-glass with fibers in +45- and -45-directions. The matrix material in both cases is polyester, Joton Norpol 72M-85. A 50% fibre weight fraction is considered for the laminates and the attachment lap. Their mechanical properties are given [6] in Table 1. In addition the interlaminar shear strength is specified to be 25 (MPa).

The core material is PVC-foam, Divinycell H100. The PVC-foam core is a microscopically homogeneous and isotropic material, with properties given in Table 2. The density of the core material is verified in [6]. The core material H100 is a material that yields in a plastic fashion.

The glue material used is Crestomer 1152 PA. This is a thixotropic resin, suitable for structural fillet in FRP marine applications, with properties as given in Table 3.

TABLE 1 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FOR E-GLASS/POLYESTER LAMINATE [6]

Longitudinal/Transverse Young's modulus (MPa)	10000/10000
Shear modulus (MPa)	6800
Longitudinal/Transverse tensile strength (MPa)	73/73
Longitudinal/Transverse compressive strength (MPa)	129/129
Shear strength (MPa)	93
Longitudinal/Transverse Poisson's ratio	0.43

TABLE 2 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF DIVINYCELL PVC-H100 AT 20°C [7]

Density (kg/m ³):	102
E-modulus compression, ASTM D1621 (MPa)	130
Ultimate compressive strength, ASTM D1621 (MPa)	1.7
E-modulus tension, ASTM D1623 (MPa)	105
Ultimate tensile strength, ASTM D1623 (MPa)	3.1
Shear modulus at 20°C, ASTM C273 (MPa)	4.2
Ultimate shear strength, ASTM C273 (MPa)	1.5

TABLE 3 TYPICAL PROPERTIES OF CRESTOMER 1152 PA [8]

Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	26
Elongation at break (%)	100
Initial tensile modulus (MPa)	500
Yield stress at 7% strain (MPa)	17

4. ANALYSIS MODEL

The T-joint (Figs. 2 and 4) is analysed using the Finite Element Method FEM, considering a plane model of the joint. Because of high stress gradients along the glue and around the interface corners, a fairly fine mesh consisting of triangular and quadrilateral elements, shown in Fig. 5, is applied. The assumption of plane strain is justified throughout, since the joint between the two sandwich panels is wide compared with its thickness and since the glue fillet area is of primary interest. Taking into consideration the symmetry only the half of the T-joint is considered. The dimensions of the T-joint and the

imposed constraints are shown in Fig. 4. The thickness of the laminates is 2.1 mm, the core thickness is 50 mm and the total span is 225 mm, in order to simulate the actual testing conditions. The glue thickness between the two sandwich panels is 1.5 mm while the radius of the attachment lap in the glue-fillet area is taken to be $(14.5+t)$ mm, where t is the thickness of the lap and α the length of the lap, see Fig. 4.

The finite element analysis is performed with the use of the general purpose finite element program ABAQUS [9]. The mesh used for the T-joint has 2018 nodes and 2062 two-dimensional elements (586 laminate, 1273 core, 203 glue elements). The bottom-laminate of panel B is modelled by one row of elements whereas the top-laminates of the panel B and the laminate of panel A are modelled by two rows of elements. The lap in the glue area is also modelled by two rows of elements (Fig. 5).

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis is carried out for a T-joint with $\alpha = 60$ mm, $t = 0.525$ mm (one layer in the attachment lap) and a $P = 20$ KN corresponding to a load level where the global behaviour still is fairly linear (Fig. 6) [6]. Selected results are shown in Figs. 7-10.

The distributions of the normal stresses σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and the shear stress σ_{xy} in the middle plane of the glue between the two panels is shown in Fig. 7. It is observed that the normal stresses are predominantly tensile, with peak values occurring near the corner A because of the discontinuity caused by the corner and because of the loaded laminate. The maximum normal stresses σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} adjacent to A are smaller than the yield stress of the glue (Table 3). Also there is a high stress level near the corner C. The values of σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} near C are smaller than those near A.

The normal stresses σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} and the shear stress σ_{xy} distributions in the middle plane of the attachment lap are shown in Fig. 8. The stress σ_{xx} increases rapidly from zero near the corner D to a maximum value in the middle of the glue-fillet area and then decreases and becomes compressive near the end of the lap in the panel B. The highest σ_{yy} -stress exists near the corner D between the lap and the laminate of the panel A. This stress concentration decreases towards the root of the lap, and

it becomes zero for the rest of the lap in the panel B. The shear stress increases from zero to a maximum negative value around the middle of the glue-fillet area, and afterwards it decreases towards the root of the lap, and it becomes zero for the rest of the lap in the panel B. The highest values of σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} are about two times the applied normal stress in the panel A laminate.

Fig. 9 shows the stress distributions in the middle plane of the core of panel B. σ_{yy} is larger than σ_{xx} and its maximum value occurs in the area where the axial forces carried by the laminate of panel A are transmitted into panel B. There is another, smaller peak of σ_{yy} near the ends where the boundary conditions are imposed. Its maximum values are smaller than the tensile strength of the core material (Table 2). The shear stress is seen to have a maximum value of 1.0 (MPa) over a relatively long part of panel B, as expected according to simple bending theory, assuming all shear force to be carried by the core. The maximum shear stress is close to the ultimate shear strength of the core material (Table 2).

Fig. 10 displays the stress distributions in the core of the panel A near to the interface with the glue ($Y = 56.012$). It is observed that there are high stress gradients near the interface corner A, where the core, the laminate and the glue meet. The highest stresses σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} are lower than the ultimate tensile strength, but the highest shear stress is very close to the ultimate shear strength of the core material (Table 2).

From this numerical investigation it follows that the overall stresses are relatively small compared to the material strength around the interface corners B, C and D and that the main problem appears at the interface corner A where the highest stress concentrations occur. In addition, the most critical stress for the T-joint relative to the ultimate material strength, is in shear, for the core of the panel A near the interface corner where the three materials meet. There is a problem with shear, in the core of the panel B, too. The above stress analysis only gives an indication of the failure mode that takes place in the T-joint under pull-out loads. Core and glue are materials that yield plastically, so further research is required in order to predict the failure mode exactly. Also more work is required to

find out the influence of defects in the glue on the efficiency of the T-joint.

6. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1. Connection between two sandwich panels

FIGURE 2. Experimental set-up for pull-out test

FIGURE 3. Geometry of the attachment lap area and possible defects

FIGURE 4. Overall model with boundary conditions

FIGURE 5. Finite element mesh of the glue-fillet area (G.F. in Fig. 4)

FIGURE 6. Load-displacement curve for a T-joint with $\alpha = 60$ mm

FIGURE 7. Stress distributions in the middle plane of the glue between the two panels

FIGURE 8. Stress distributions in the middle plane of the attachment lap

FIGURE 9. Stress distributions in the middle plane of the core of panel B

FIGURE 10. Stress distributions in the core of panel A for $Y = 56.012$ mm